

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

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ABSTRACT: This study was undertaken to determine the level of parents' involvement in terms of parental support and reading activities; to determine the pupils' reading ability using Phil-IRI Posttest Results for School Year: 2023 – 2024 and to determine level of general average for School Year: 2023-2024; to determine how parents' involvement affects their children's reading proficiency and overall average. The study was conducted to five small elementary schools of Libona District, Division of Bukidnon with One Hundred Nineteen (119) Grade 6 pupils' parents as actual respondents. The study employed documentary analysis in conjunction with the descriptive correlational methodology. The study used an adapted research questionnaire for the parents' involvement variable that passed the validity and reliability tests. Statistical tools like Mean and Standard Deviation, Frequency and Percentage and Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient for the analysis of the gathered data were used. Results showed that overall level of parents' involvement was High while overall pupils' level of reading ability was Instructional and their general average was Satisfactory. Significant low to moderate positive correlation was observed between parents' involvement and pupils' reading ability and general average. Thus, parents may maintain their high level of involvement to the pupils' development of reading ability. It is recommended that assistance and support to the pupils in their reading must be provided and participation in different school activities must also be given time by the parents.

KEYWORDS: general average, parents' involvement, reading ability

I. INTRODUCTION

The degree of literacy is one of the most accurate measures of academic achievement. Children who have difficulty reading initially when they first enter school usually stay that way throughout their scholastic careers. This study's objective is to look into how parental involvement affects the children's reading ability and general average or performance. Parents' participation can improve children's accomplishments and performance with regards to reading.

Reading is the most crucial ability taught in school and acquired by pupils. It serves as the entrance to all other forms of knowledge. The primary responsibility given to elementary schools is to instruct pupils in reading so that they can read proficiently by the conclusion of their third grade. Therefore, it is crucial for individuals to acquire proficiency in reading, which is considered one of the fundamental life skills and a macro talent. It allows individuals to be proactive, autonomous thinkers who take charge of their own learning (Par, 2020). It is also a component of one's cognitive processes, aiding in the interpretation and resolution of inquiries. Reading cultivates a deep appreciation and admiration for various aspects of life, including literature, arts, folklores, and the environment. Engaging in reading transports individuals to various locations and expands their imaginative capacity. This skill enables individuals to comprehend many concepts in the fields of education and society.

Reading has many additional significant advantages outside just being a useful skill for knowledge acquisition. Young and elderly readers who are actively reading are frequently conscious of the knowledge they pick up from a text, but they might not be aware of all the other important abilities they are developing at the same time. Reading has many advantages, one of which is improving one's linguistic abilities, particularly if the reading content combines simple and complex ideas. Reading improves one's capacity to talk and write through advancing one's vocabulary, grammar, and syntax (Abril et al., 2022).

Reading is a crucial ability for enabling people to gain from human knowledge and experience, as mentioned by Cerbito et al. (2020). Being unable to read deprives someone of the ability to learn facts, distinguish between what is and is not credible, and comprehend the world around them. Reading has played a significant role in the advancement of humankind. Reading is a

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

skill that parents have instilled in their children to better their future. But as the systems have evolved, some problems have emerged that have made reading challenging for many pupils, especially in this generation.

Pergar and Hadela (2020), in this day and age, there is, without a doubt, an emphasis placed on the significance of reading to children beginning at a young age. Even if current technology is present in every aspect of children's education, it is important to remember that reading plays a crucial part in children's future development and learning, both cognitively and emotionally. This is something that should not be overlooked. Reading is, therefore a particularly valuable exercise for English language learners. The benefits of reading apply to their language journey, even if the goal is, for instance, fluency in speaking. However, it can be difficult to find reading material that is accessible, challenging, and relevant to an English language learner, making quality reading material a valuable resource. This is because parents' priorities are on the basic needs of the pupils and at home, and sometimes their income can no longer support other needs like providing additional reading materials and even ample time for assisting and guiding their pupils in doing their tasks, reading practices, and homework. It shows that learners who struggle in reading are the ones who have less supportive parents while learners who are good at reading are the ones whose parents follow up their studies at home (Bano et al., 2020). The achievement of their children can be significantly impacted by the involvement of their parents in their education. Research indicated that children who have parents who are also involved in their children's education perform better academically, attend class more frequently, and achieve higher scores on standardized examinations. (Castillo et al., 2020).

Helping with homework, attending school functions, participating in school decision-making, and keeping lines of communication open with teachers are just a few ways parents can support their children's education. One of the most obvious benefits of parental involvement in a child's education is helping them with their schoolwork. (Romero et al., 2020). Children who receive homework assistance from their parents are more likely to understand the material and be ready to perform well on any associated tests or assignments. Along with helping with homework, parents may be able to identify their children's areas of difficulty and support them in improving those areas (Xu et al., 2020).

Another excellent way for parents to support their child's education is by attending school plays, parent-teacher conferences, and other school functions. In addition to learning more about their child's academic achievement and potential obstacles, parents can attend these events to show their support for the school and their education (Duxbury et al., 2021). Parental engagement also includes being heard and considered during decision-making. Parents can play an active role in their children's education by assisting in the selection of a suitable school or educational program, participating in the creation of an Early Intervention Program EIP (if one is required), and speaking up for their child's unique needs (Kaden, 2020). Involving parents in decision-making is important because it allows them to guarantee that their child receives an education that is individualized to his or her requirements and that the child has access to the resources necessary for success.

The problem is particularly in rural schools with a high composition of children from minority groups and economically low-income households. This applies also to the indigenous people living in the rural areas. The reading progress of children nationwide indicates that children from many of the ethnic groups fail to read at grade level. Struggling to read during the elementary school years has long-term consequences for children that include a lack of frustration, self-confidence, low academic performance, and motivation to learn that, leads to dropping out of school and problem behaviors.

This premise encouraged the researcher to determine the parents' involvement in the reading ability and academic performance through a general average of Grade 6 pupils. The data would also serve as one of the bases for planning, designing/redesigning the reading programs or activities in the school to improve the overall school reading performance.

The Metacognition Theory developed by John Flavell served as the foundation for this research project. According to Hague (2019), John Flavell was the first person to characterize metacognition as the concept of awareness and management of thought. The need for metacognition, also referred to as "thinking about our thinking," was emphasized throughout the presentation. The concept of metacognition is analogous to that of an unseen guide who resides in a particular region of the brain. According to Ganapati and Mostafavi (2021), this mentor can obtain information on how an individual thinks and evaluates the functioning of the individual's brain. This acknowledges the limitations of the individual's understanding and helps in the development of specific measures that are more straightforward.

The study conducted by Veas et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of metacognitive strategies in early childhood for academic achievement. It emphasized that parental involvement is crucial for the future development of adolescents and served as a model for education. The implementation of metacognitive strategies significantly impacted pupils' performance in reading comprehension. It enhanced pupils' reading skills and their ability to fully utilize their reading abilities.

This study was anchored on Eldeeb's (2018) study, which established a positive relationship between academic achievement and parental involvement. The study discussed further that the school must seek the support of the community members to further its developmental programs for engagements between the school, parents, and community. There should be more involvement from the parents and community in decision-making for the benefit of the learners.

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

Furthermore, the research adhered to DepEd Order No. 014, s. 2018, commonly referred to as the "Every Child a Reader Program". This plan seeks to transform every Filipino child into a proficient reader and writer appropriate for their grade level. Both English and Filipino, through oral reading, silent reading, and listening comprehension, assessed the reading proficiency of pupils. This is by the 2018 document titled "Policy Guidelines of the Administration of the Revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory to Enhance the Overall Reading Performance of the School." In addition to serving as a foundation for organizing and planning the reading instruction delivered by the instructors and the programs or activities provided by the school, the Phil-IRI data is also utilized in this regard.

II. METHODOLOGY

Using documentary analysis, the process of reviewing or evaluating documents in conjunction with the descriptive correlational methodology, the researcher conducted the study. Documentary analysis is the process of obtaining available data at school where the researcher utilized for this study. The researcher was able to utilize correlational statistics to evaluate and quantify the strength of connections among components or collections of scores while doing correlational research. This type of study was characterized by a descriptive correlational design that employed a quantitative method that did not include experimentation (Asenahabi, 2019). In addition, the descriptive correlational methodology utilized in this study provided the opportunity to collect data regarding the respondents' parents' involvement as well as the tactics that pupils employ when reading to improve their reading ability.

The researcher gathered the data, they were compiled, sorted, organized and tabulated. They were subject to statistical treatment in order to answer the questions proposed in this study. The statistical tools employed were the Mean, Standard Deviation to find out the level of parents' involvement. Frequency, Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation to find out the reading ability and academic performance of the pupils. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to determine the significant relationship among parental involvement, reading ability and reading performance.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Problem 1. What is the level of parental involvement in terms of:

- 1.1 parental support; and
- 1.2 reading activities?

Table 1 presents the overall level of parental involvement. It reveals that it has an overall Mean of 3.96 with SD=0.55, described as Agree and interpreted as Highly Involved. This implies that parents greatly involved in children's reading performance and consistently demonstrates that parental involvement links to better learning outcomes. Parents assistance given to the pupils must not only focus on providing their basic needs but even in supporting their studies. This will help the pupil realized that they are not alone and that they have somebody to lean on. This will further make the pupils more inspired and motivated to learn and achieve more specially in reading.

Table 1: Overall Parental Involvement

Variables	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Parental Support	4.07	0.54	Agree	Highly Involved
Reading Activities	3.84	0.56	Agree	Highly Involved
Overall Mean	3.96	0.55	Agree	Highly Involved

Note: 4.20 – 5.00 Very Highly Involved
3.41 – 4.20 Highly Involved
2.61 – 3.40 Moderately Involved
1.81 – 2.60 Less Involved
1.00 – 1.80 Least Involved

According to Tran et al., (2020) Children's achievement can be significantly impacted by parents' participation and interest in their education. Research indicates that children who have parents who are also involved in their education perform better academically, attend class more frequently, and achieve higher scores on standardized examinations (Castillo et al.,2020). Helping with homework, going to school functions, participating in school decision-making, and keeping lines of communication open with teachers are just a few ways parents can support their kids' education (Cusinato et al., 2020).

While there are many benefits to parents being involved in their children's education, helping with homework is one of the most obvious. (Romero et al. 2020). When parents assist their children with their homework, they may make sure that their

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

children understand the material completely and are ready to perform well on any associated tests or assignments. (Emm-Collison et al., 2019).

Moreover, parental support, has the highest Mean of 4.07 with SD=0.54, describes as Agree and interpreted as Highly Involved. This finding implies that children's academic motivation and school attitudes have been found to improve when parents participate more. Family issues or socioeconomic issues may impair a pupils' academic achievement, although parents' involvement can serve as a protective barrier against these effects.

The authors Stefansen and Smette (2018) emphasized that profound engagement serves as a clear illustration of various parental cultivation concepts and the associated responsibilities that parents today must navigate. For instance, creating conducive conditions is increasingly vital as it can enhance academic performance. It appears that parents influence their children's success by fostering a warm and supportive environment and establishing high expectations for their academic achievements.

On the other hand, reading activities has the lowest Mean of 3.84 with SD=0.56, described as Agree and interpreted as Highly Involved. This finding implies that taking part in activities such as reading to children or participating in educational activities at home, such as singing or playing games with family members, consistently associated favorably with early children's academic progress. Parents' assistance and guidance on the pupils' reading activities at home is essential so that what the pupils did and learn at school will be reviewed at home and that mastery towards the certain lesson will be solidified through constant practice at home with the presence of their parents.

According to Noviante and Garzia (2020), the home environment is a key component that promotes learning and improves children's education. This includes the engagement of children in academic activities such as parent-child connections, as well as relations and educational accessibility and reading activities. It is crucial for parents to make their children's education a priority. Children are still in their developmental stage, therefore they need guidance and assistance as well as unconditional love and care for their parents and even family members.

Parents' engagement in their children's schooling can have a profound effect on their children's success (Tran et al., 2020). Studies demonstrate that pupils do better academically, attend school more regularly, and score higher on standardized tests when their parents are also invested in their education (Castillo et al., 2020). Parents can support their children's learning in a variety of ways, including by assisting with homework, attending school events, being active in school decision-making, and maintaining open lines of communication with instructors (Cusinato et al., 2020). Parental involvement in a child's education has many positive effects, but one of the most tangible is assistance with homework (Romero et al., 2020). Parents who help their kids with homework are better able to ensure that their offspring fully grasp the concepts at hand and are prepared to do well on any related examinations or homework (Emm-Collison et al., 2019). As an added bonus, parents who assist with homework may be able to spot problem areas and help their child improve in those areas (Xu et al., 2020).

Problem 2. What is the pupils' level of reading ability using Phil-IRI Posttest Results for School Year 2023 – 2024?

Table 2: Pupils' Reading Ability

Level	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Independent	52	43.70			
Instructional	34	28.58	2.16	0.62	Instructional
Frustration	33	27.72			
Total	119	100.00			

Note: 2.33 – 3.00 Independent 1.67 – 2.32 Instructional 1.00 – 1.66 Frustration

Table 2 presents the level of pupils' reading ability using PHIL-IRI results for School Year 2023-2024. It reveals that it has an overall Mean of 2.16 with SD=0.62, which describe and interpreted as Instructional Level. This finding implies that there are pupils that have not fully developed their reading skills, capacity and capability. Instructional reading level is the second to the highest level of reading at which a reader is not independent, but has adequate background knowledge for a topic, and can access text quickly and with no or few errors. Although the pupils at this level need little assistance, the teachers should not slack in guiding and assisting them so that they will surely elevate their reading level.

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) test result of the Grade 6 pupils. The result showed the Pupils' Reading Literacy Level as Independent at which a pupil can read independently and with ease without the help or guidance of the teacher. The next level is the Instructional – it is the level at which readers profit the most from teacher instruction in reading. And the last level is the Frustration – It is the level at which readers find reading materials so difficult that they cannot successfully respond to them. The result further showed that there were 119 Grade VI Pupils who have been administered based on the result their scores were interpreted and they were categorized as independent with Frequency of 52 and a Percentage of 43.70, instructional with Frequency of 34 with a Percentage of 28.58, and frustration with Frequency of 33 and a Percentage of 27.72.

This tool utilized in determining the reading level of the pupils is supported by DepEd Order No.14 s. 2018 that provides the guidelines for the administration of the revised Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI). The tool is administered for Grades 3 to 6 learners in public elementary schools nationwide. As of this time, it is still the most recognized tool to determine the reading level of the learners.

Reading level of the pupils should be given more attention and action as it forms an integral part of the pupils' learning development. Studies have shown that one of the reasons why pupils have low performance in academics as well as on international exams or evaluations is because of their low comprehension level. Nowadays, there are various reading related activities conducted and implemented so that pupils with low reading level can improve and catch up with their peers that are in the higher reading level. It is said that when a pupil struggles with reading capacity and capability, it is likely that they will struggle performing the tasks assigned from other subjects as well (Inding, 2020).

Problem 3. What is the pupils' general average for School Year 2023-2024?

This table 3 presents the level of general average for school year: 2023-2024 in which the General Average is computed by dividing the sum of all final grades by the total number of learning areas. Each learning area has equal weight. The Final Grade in each learning area and the General Average are reported as whole numbers. The data reveal that the overall Mean is 84.91 with SD=1.99, described and interpreted as Satisfactory Level or majority of the 119 pupils belong to outstanding with 31.93 percent. However, there were a lot of pupils' performances that is quite low as there were pupils that have the performance at passing grades or slightly above the passing mark.

When pupils perform low with their academics, the teachers must be vigilant on these cases as well as on being active in providing assistance and guidance for the pupils via remediations and provision of extra activities. Teachers and parents can collaborate to make sure that the pupils are given attention and assistance at school and most importantly at home for better reinforcements Affuso (2022). Pupils struggling with their reading and academic performance must be given due attention and help because it means that there are concepts and competencies that they missed to master in full. In the spiraling method of education that is ideal for the k to 12 curriculum it is fitting that each pupil should master the necessary skills and competencies as they progress to the higher grade level DepEd Order no.15 s.2015.

Table 3: Pupils' General Average

Level	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Outstanding	38	31.93			
Very Satisfactory	23	19.32			
Satisfactory	27	22.68	84.91	1.99	Satisfactory
Fairly Satisfactory	30	25.21			
Did not meet expectations	1	0.86			
Total	119	100.00			

Note: 90-100 Outstanding 85 – 89 Very Satisfactory 80 – 84 Satisfactory
75 – 79 Fairly Satisfactory 74 & below Did not Meet Expectations

According to Par (2020) the pupils must be taught with the various reading skills and strategies as they progress to higher level of education and learning because as the grade level go higher the lessons that they need to study and learn also becomes more challenging. With a lot of reading strategies, the pupils can select which of the strategies that they will use to better learn and understand the lessons that they are facing and studying.

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

Problem 4. Is there significant relationship between parents' involvement and pupils' reading ability?

Table 4: Correlation Between Parental Involvement and Pupils' Reading Ability

Variables	r-value	p-value	Level of Correlation	Decision	Interpretation
Parental Support	0.421	0.001	Low Positive Correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Reading Activities	0.549	0.001	Moderate Positive Correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Note:	0.91 - 1.00 Very High Positive Correlation		0.71 – 0.90 High Positive Correlation		
	0.51 – 0.70 Moderate Positive Correlation		0.31 – 0.50 Low Positive Correlation		
	0.00 – 0.30 Negligible Positive Correlation		<i>Significant when computed p-value <0.05</i>		

Table 4 shows the test relationship between parents' involvement and pupils' reading ability. Parents' involvement which includes parental support and reading activities is the independent variable and pupils' reading ability is the dependent variable. For parental support, it registered an r-value of 0.421 with computed p-value of 0.001. The computed p-value is less than the critical p-value. This data imply that significant low positive correlation was registered between parents' involvement and pupils' reading ability when parents' support is taken into action. Though the relationship is low, the relationship between the two (2) variables was observe. This further means that as the level of parents' involvement will increase there is also minimal possibility that score for reading ability will also increases. Thus, it is important to have recognized it.

Data revealed that moderate positive correlation was registered between parents' involvement towards pupils' reading ability. This simply indicates that parents play a vital role in the development of the pupils. Therefore, they must find time to be with them and assist them in their educational activities.

Leander & Fabella (2020) stated that parents' engagement to pupils' activities specially in reading at home is crucial. The child becomes more confident and inspired to read and study if their parents are helping them and are ready to assist their needs. Parents must be engaged to the activities of their pupils despite tiredness and exhaustion from work. A simple question of asking how was the pupil's day at school and what did they do while in the school can make the pupil feel valued and important.

For reading activities, it registered an r-value of 0.549 with computed p-value of 0.001. The computed p-value is less than the critical p-value. This data imply that significant moderate positive correlation was registered between parental involvement and pupils' reading ability when reading activities is taken into account. Although the relationship or the connection is at moderate level only, the relationship between the two variables was observable. This means that as the level of parents' involvement increase there is also possibility that score for reading ability also increases. Thus, it is important to have recognition and give importance to it.

Reading activities is important in developing the pupils' reading ability Ntekane (2018). Through constant and consistent reading activities and practices the pupils become acquainted with words that are common and even those that are unfamiliar to them. They get to know the meaning and uses of it in the sentences. Reading allows the pupils to exercise their brain not just in mastering their reading ability but even on comprehending and even on making imaginations as to the possible next scenario or ending of the story or selection that they read.

According to Vergara et al. (2019) Pupils have the opportunity to improve their reading skills and abilities through reading activities. Parents and teachers should encourage and help their children to completely appreciate the lovely story and even the information they are reading. These days, there are a lot of opportunities for pupils to improve their reading skills. Still, one of the greatest ways to inspire and motivate children is to have their parents and teachers be there to guide them.

Problem 5. Is there significant relationship between parents' involvement and pupils' general average?

Table 5: Correlation Between Parental Involvement and Pupils' General Average

Variables	r-value	p-value	Level of Correlation	Decision	Interpretation
Parental Support	0.392	0.003	Low Positive Correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Reading Activities	0.516	0.001	Moderate Positive Correlation	Reject Ho	Significant
Note:	0.91 - 1.00 Very High Positive Correlation		0.71 – 0.90 High Positive Correlation		
	0.51 – 0.70 Moderate Positive Correlation		0.31	–	0.50 Low Positive Correlation
	0.00 – 0.30 Negligible Positive Correlation		<i>Significant when computed p-value <0.05</i>		

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

This table 5 reveals the correlation between parental involvement and pupils' general average. The statistical analysis revealed that the r-value for parental support was 0.392, and the p-value was determined to be 0.003. There is a difference between the computed p-value and the critical p-value. This data suggest that a low positive connection was detected between parental engagement and pupils' general average when parental support is taken into consideration. Also, this correlation was shown to be significant. The association between the two (2) variables was evident, despite the fact that the connection or interaction between them is not particularly strong. This also indicates that there is a possibility that the score for reading ability will also increase as the level of parental participation improves. This is a very minor likelihood.

In light of this, it is essential to attribute recognition to it. The findings indicated that there was a moderately positive link between parental participation and the overall average of the pupils. To put it simply, this demonstrates that parents play a significant part in the growth and development of their children. Therefore, it is necessary for them to carve out time to be with them and provide assistance to them in their educational endeavors. Pergar and Hadela (2020) emphasized the the value of parents participating in their children's activities, particularly when it comes to reading exercises at home. Pupils typically gain confidence and show more willingness to read and study when their parents actively encourage them and attend to their requirements. Parents are urged to participate in their children's activities regardless of how exhausted they are from work.

A simple inquiry, such as asking about their day at school and what they experienced during their time there, can significantly enhance pupils' sense of worth and importance.

For reading activities, it registered an r-value of 0.516 with computed p-value of 0.001. The computed p-value is less than the critical p-value. This data imply that significant moderate positive correlation was registered between parental involvement and pupils' general average when reading activities is taken into account. Although the relationship or the connection is at moderate level only, the relationship between the two (2) variables was observable. This further means that as the level of parents' involvement increase there is also possibility that the score for general average will also increases. Thus, it is important to give importance to it.

Participating in reading activities is essential for the development of the pupils' overall average Ntekane (2018). By engaging in reading tasks and techniques on a regular and consistent basis, pupils are able to become familiar with terms that are common as well as words that are foreign to them. This will result in a higher level of comprehension, which is essential for acquiring knowledge in other subject areas. They find out what it means and how it is utilized in the phrases, and they are able to determine which answer is the most appropriate to apply and employ in the process of fixing the problem. Reading provides pupils with the opportunity to exercise their brains not only in terms of mastering their reading abilities, but also in terms of comprehending and even in terms of making imaginations regarding the probable next scenario or finish of the tale or selection that they read.

Ormilla (2021) stated that parents' involvement to pupils' activities at school have better impact to the pupil's morale and sense of belongingness and eventually their performance in academics. Pupils are proud when they see their parents behind their back at school. They feel secure that whatever happens they have their parents and family to support and guide them. Finally, the results of moderate positive correlation between parental involvements towards the pupils' academic performance indicated that when there is increase of parental engagement it will also mean increase on the reading performance of the pupils. Thus, parents should be made aware of their importance to their pupils.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this study, following conclusions are formulated:

1. Parents were highly involved on the pupils' educational activities indicating their consistent support, guidance and assistance for them.
2. Pupils reading ability signifies readiness for higher level of studies.
3. Pupils' general average was just above the passing mark emphasizing the need for improvement and consistency on their study, activities and habits.
4. Parents are involve in the reading activities of their children.
5. Reading activities was crucial for the pupils' reading ability and general average.

V. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions generated from this study, the researcher has formulated the following recommendations:

1. Parents may maintain their high level of involvement to the pupils' development of reading ability. They will continually support particularly their children's reading activities and participate in different school activities.

Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

2. Pupils with independent reading ability may sustain it. Intervention activities for reading may be conducted both at school and at home to ensure consistent learning development and study habits.
3. Pupils' may continue to improve their general average. Teachers and parents should continue to provide their children with emotional and financial support, communication, and remain active in their lives.
4. Parents' involvement and the reading ability of pupils should be consistently partnered. The school administration may offer teachers and parents training sessions on a range of reading activities and tactics to ensure that the pupils receive thorough instruction and reinforcement both at school and at home.
5. Parents' involvement and pupils' general average should be given priorities and attention so that proper intervention programs and activities will be crafted and implemented. Thus, parents should be made aware of their importance to their pupils.

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Parents' Involvement on Pupils' Reading Ability and General Average

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